

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EXTREME GRADIENT BOOSTING AND LIGHT GRADIENT BOOSTING MACHINE CLASSIFICATION ON STUNTING DATA IN EAST NUSA TENGGARA

Desi Natalia Muskananfolo^{1*} and Abdurakhman¹

¹Mathematics Department, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural
Science, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Sekip Utara Bulaksumur,
Yogyakarta, 55281, Indonesia.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s):

desinataliamuskananfolo@mail.ugm.ac.id;

Contributing authors: rachmanstat@ugm.ac.id;

Abstract

Stunting is a significant public health issue in Indonesia, affecting children's physical and cognitive growth. In 2021, Nusa Tenggara Timur (NTT) recorded the highest stunting prevalence in Indonesia at 37.8%. This study compares the performance of *Extreme Gradient Boosting* (XGBoost) and *Light Gradient Boosting Machine* (LightGBM) algorithms in detecting stunting among children in NTT. The data underwent *preprocessing*, including *data cleaning*, *label encoding*, handling imbalance with SMOTE, and *splitting data*. Evaluations were conducted using data splits of 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40, with metrics such as *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall*, *F1-Score*, and *Area Under the Curve* (AUC). Results show XGBoost outperformed LightGBM in classification performance, achieving *accuracy* of 93.11%, *precision* of 91.70%, *recall* of 95.61%, *F1-Score* of 93.62%, and AUC of 0.9848 on the 80:20 split. Conversely, LightGBM demonstrated superior computational efficiency with nearly ten times faster training time, though with lower performance (*accuracy* of 82.96%, AUC of 0.9072). Furthermore, this study evaluated the alignment of stunting data in NTT with the Ministry of Health and WHO standards, finding an agreement rate of 83.57%. In conclusion, XGBoost

excels in classification accuracy, while LightGBM is more efficient in computation time, making them complementary tools for stunting analysis.

Keywords: Stunting, East Nusa Tenggara, XGBoost, LightGBM, SMOTE

1 Introduction

Stunting remains a significant public health issue in Indonesia and is a top priority in national health policies. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics [2] and the Ministry of Health, the national stunting prevalence in 2021 reached 24.4%, with the province of East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) recording the highest prevalence at 37.8%. Stunting is a chronic form of malnutrition caused by prolonged inadequate nutritional intake, especially during the first 1,000 days of life. It is measured based on children's height and weight being below the standard for their age [34].

The impact of stunting extends beyond individuals, affecting economic and social growth. Stunted children are at higher risk of developmental delays, lower academic performance, and poor economic productivity in adulthood. Thus, interventions to reduce stunting rates are crucial, particularly in regions with high prevalence, such as NTT [2]. Consequently, reducing stunting prevalence has become a priority in national health strategies.

In recent years, advancements in technology have enabled the application of *machine learning* methods to predict health problems. This approach is valuable in identifying factors contributing to stunting and predicting the risk of stunting occurrence. Two popular *machine learning* algorithms commonly used for health classification problems are *Extreme Gradient Boosting* (XGBoost)

and *Light Gradient Boosting Machine* (LightGBM), which excel in processing high-dimensional data with superior predictive performance [5, 13].

Machine learning is a branch of computer science that uses past experiences to learn and apply its knowledge to make future decisions [7]. XGBoost is an *ensemble learning* method that combines multiple *decision trees* and iteratively adds new trees to correct previous errors. This algorithm is highly popular due to its speed and efficiency in producing accurate predictions. Compared to other *Gradient Boosting Machine* (GBM) methods, XGBoost performs optimization up to ten times faster [5]. Similarly, LightGBM is widely used in health classification problems. LightGBM, a variant of *Gradient Boosting Decision Tree* (GBDT), is designed to handle large-scale data quickly and efficiently. For example, [26] used LightGBM to detect thyroid disease, achieving a training accuracy of 1 and a testing accuracy of 0.9975. Compared to conventional GBM methods, LightGBM operates up to 20 times faster during training without sacrificing accuracy [13].

Previous studies have shown that XGBoost and LightGBM perform excellently in predicting health issues. For instance, [33] found that XGBoost was more effective in identifying patients at risk of *Acute Kidney Injury* (AKI) than logistic regression. In another study, [21] compared LightGBM with algorithms such as *k-Nearest Neighbors* (kNN), *Support Vector Machines* (SVM), *Naive*

Bayes (NB), *Bagging*, and *Random Forest* (RF) for diagnosing diabetes mellitus. The results indicated that LightGBM had higher accuracy (98.1%) compared to *Random Forest* (96.9%) and was more efficient in memory usage. While XGBoost and LightGBM have been widely applied in various health problems, their application in predicting stunting in Indonesia remains limited. [1] noted that factors such as economic status, maternal education, and access to health services influence stunting incidence in Indonesia, but the application of predictive algorithms like XGBoost and LightGBM in this analysis requires further exploration.

Based on the aforementioned discussion, the *Extreme Gradient Boosting* (XGBoost) and *Light Gradient Boosting Machine* (LightGBM) methods are capable of addressing classification problems effectively. Therefore, this study aims to compare the performance of XGBoost and LightGBM algorithms in predicting stunting in East Nusa Tenggara using evaluation metrics such as *accuracy*, *sensitivity*, *specificity*, *precision*, and *Area Under the Curve* (AUC). This research is expected to provide new insights into classifying stunting data among children under five years old in East Nusa Tenggara and serve as a foundation for developing further strategies to prevent and reduce stunting prevalence in the region.

2 Methods

2.1 Baseline Methods

2.1.1 Machine Learning

Machine learning is a branch of computer science that utilizes past experiences to learn and apply the knowledge for future decision-making. It intersects the fields of

computer science, engineering, and statistics.

Fig. 1 Intersection of computer science, engineering, and statistics.

Machine learning is broadly categorized into three categories. The main categories are supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning [7].

2.1.2 Supervised Learning

Supervised learning is a foundational approach in machine learning that focuses on predicting target variables by learning from labeled data. The primary goal is to identify relationships between predictors (features) and the target variable (response) based on historical data. [24].

Fig. 2 Working Mechanism of Supervised Learning.

Supervised learning is not only used for prediction but also for understanding

the relationships between predictors and responses. Some features in a dataset may not be relevant. Machine learning models can identify significant features while discarding those that introduce noise [24].

2.1.3 Decision Tree

A decision tree is a type of supervised learning algorithm that works with predefined target variables and is commonly used in classification problems. It is highly effective for classification tasks and can handle both continuous and categorical input variables. Decision trees aim to identify the most significant variable and its value to split the dataset into homogeneous subsets [27].

2.1.4 Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE)

SMOTE is a technique used to address class imbalance by generating synthetic samples for the minority class through interpolation. It selects nearest neighbors for each minority sample and generates new samples along the line segment connecting the sample and its neighbors [29]. Given data with p variables $x^T = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p]$ and $z^T = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_p]$, the Euclidean distance is calculated as follows:

$$d(x, z) = \sqrt{(x_1 - z_1)^2 + \dots + (x_p - z_p)^2} \quad (1)$$

Synthetic samples are generated using the following equation:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{syn}} = \mathbf{x}_i + (\mathbf{x}_{\text{knn}} - \mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \gamma \quad (2)$$

Where:

- \mathbf{x}_{syn} : Synthetic data.
- \mathbf{x}_i : Minority class sample.

- \mathbf{x}_{knn} : Nearest neighbor sample.
- γ : Random number between 0 and 1.

Fig. 3 Illustration of SMOTE.

The generated synthetic data is illustrated in Figure 3, where green points represent synthetic samples added to balance the dataset.

2.1.5 Hyperparameter Tuning Using Grid Search

To achieve an optimal model, hyperparameter tuning is essential for configuring parameter values in machine learning methods. Hyperparameter tuning adjusts various aspects of machine learning, significantly impacting the performance and outcome of the model [6]. One popular method for hyperparameter tuning is the grid search method. Grid search combines all possible values based on predefined parameters to identify the parameter values with the best evaluation results for the model, thereby maximizing the classification accuracy [22]. In practice, grid search is often combined with cross-validation methods. Cross-validation originates from the split-validation model, which evaluates training errors using test data [15].

2.1.6 k-Fold Cross Validation

The *k-Fold Cross Validation* method randomly partitions the dataset D into k

mutually exclusive subsets: f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k , with each fold containing $\frac{1}{k}$ of the data. Subsequently, k datasets are constructed: D_1, D_2, \dots, D_k , each comprising $(k - 1)$ folds for training data and 1 fold for test data. For example, with $k = 5$, the dataset D_1 contains four folds: f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5 for training and f_1 for testing. Similarly, D_2 comprises folds f_1, f_3, f_4, f_5 for training and f_2 for testing. This process continues for datasets D_3, D_4, D_5 , ensuring that each fold is used as test data exactly once, as illustrated in Figure 4 [28].

Fig. 4 k -Fold Cross Validation method applied to dataset D

The mean squared error, MSE_1 , is calculated on observations in a given fold. This procedure is repeated k times, with a different group of observations serving as the validation set each time. This results in k estimates of the test error, $MSE_1, MSE_2, \dots, MSE_k$. The k -fold cross-validation error is computed as the average:

$$CV_{(k)} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k MSE_i \quad (3)$$

In practice, k -fold cross-validation is commonly performed using $k = 5$ or $k = 10$. The primary advantage of choosing $k = 5$ or $k = 10$ instead of $k = n$ is computational efficiency. Cross-validation is a widely applicable approach used in nearly all statistical learning methods. It aims to evaluate how well the statistical learning

procedure performs on data; in this case, accurate test error estimation is critical [11].

2.1.7 Gradient Boosting

Gradient boosting is one of the boosting techniques that iteratively reduces the residual errors from the previous model by optimizing the loss function. The core of this method is to improve the model's performance by minimizing the loss function $L(y, F(x))$ at each iteration. Each new model added is designed to correct the prediction errors of the previous model, thereby enhancing overall model accuracy [7].

Here is a simplified explanation of the Gradient Boosting algorithm. Initially, a model is assumed with 75% accuracy, with unexplained variance stored in the error component:

$$Y = F(x) + \text{error} \quad (4)$$

Next, another model is trained on the error component to add explanatory elements, increasing overall accuracy:

$$\text{error} = G(x) + \text{error}_2 \quad (5)$$

The resulting model accuracy improves to 80%, and the model equation becomes:

$$Y = F(x) + G(x) + \text{error}_2 \quad (6)$$

The process continues by training another model on error_2 to further refine the model's explanatory power:

$$\text{error}_2 = H(x) + \text{error}_3 \quad (7)$$

Finally, the model accuracy increases to 85%, resulting in:

$$Y = F(x) + G(x) + H(x) + \text{error}_3 \quad (8)$$

If a weighted average approach is used, where higher weights are assigned to more accurate models, prediction results can be improved even further compared to simple addition. This is the principle behind gradient boosting:

$$Y = \alpha \cdot F(x) + \beta \cdot G(x) + \gamma \cdot H(x) + \text{error}_4 \quad (9)$$

Assigning optimal weights may lead to accuracy reaching 90%, compared to only 85% with simple addition.

2.1.8 Gradient Boosting Algorithm

The Gradient Boosting algorithm involves the following steps:

1. Initialization:

$$f_0(x) = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^N L(y_i, \gamma) \quad (10)$$

The initialization step creates an initial model as a single terminal node, which will be refined in subsequent steps. The initial model is an optimal constant value used as the starting point.

2. For each $m = 1$ to M :
 - a) For $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, calculate:

$$r_{im} = - \left[\frac{\partial L(y_i, f(x_i))}{\partial f(x_i)} \right]_{f=f_{m-1}} \quad (11)$$

These residuals represent the errors in predictions from the previous model that need to be corrected. Residuals or errors are calculated by comparing the actual outcomes with previous predictions.

- b) Train a regression tree on the residuals r_{im} to obtain terminal regions R_{jm} , where $j = 1, 2, \dots, J_m$.

- c) For $j = 1, 2, \dots, J_m$, calculate:

$$\gamma_{jm} = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{x_i \in R_{jm}} L(y_i, f_{m-1}(x_i) + \gamma) \quad (12)$$

The decision tree is trained on the residuals to add explanatory power to the model.

- d) Update the model:

$$f_m(x) = f_{m-1}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^{J_m} \gamma_{jm} I(x \in R_{jm}) \quad (13)$$

where $I(x \in R_{jm})$ is an indicator function that equals 1 if x belongs to region R_{jm} , and 0 otherwise.

3. Output:

Finally, all weak learners are combined into a strong learner through an ensemble approach:

$$\hat{f}(x) = f_M(x) \quad (14)$$

2.1.9 Classification Model Evaluation

Evaluating the performance of a classification model typically involves using a test dataset, which is separate from the training data, and specific evaluation metrics. Several metrics are commonly used to evaluate classification models, including *accuracy*, *error rate*, *recall/sensitivity/true positive rate*, *specificity/true negative rate*, *precision*, *F-measure* or *F₁-score*, and *F_β* [9].

1. *Accuracy*: The proportion of correctly classified samples.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{P + N} \quad (15)$$

2. *Error rate*: The proportion of misclassified samples.

$$\text{Error} = \frac{FP + FN}{P + N} \quad (16)$$

3. *Recall* or *Sensitivity* or *True Positive Rate (TPR)*:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{P} \quad (17)$$

4. *Specificity* or *True Negative Rate (TNR)*:

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{N} \quad (18)$$

5. *Precision*: The proportion of true positive samples out of all positive predictions.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (19)$$

6. *F-measure* or *F₁-score*: The harmonic mean of *Precision* and *Recall*.

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (20)$$

7. *F_β-score*: A weighted harmonic mean of *Precision* and *Recall*, where β adjusts the weight of *Recall*.

$$F_\beta = \frac{(1 + \beta^2) \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\beta^2 \times \text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (21)$$

2.1.10 ROC Curves and AUC

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is a graphical representation of a classification model's performance, plotting the *True Positive Rate* (TPR) on the y-axis against the *False Positive Rate* (FPR) on the x-axis. An ideal classifier has a point at the top-left corner (TPR

= 1, FPR = 0), while a random classifier lies along the diagonal line $y = x$ [3]. An example of an ROC curve is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 An Example of an ROC Curve

The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) is a single scalar value summarizing the model's ability to discriminate between classes. A high AUC indicates a better-performing model. AUC is calculated using the following formula [16]:

$$AUC = \frac{1 + TPR - FPR}{2} \quad (22)$$

[8] provides the following guidelines for interpreting AUC values:

- 0.90 - 1.00: Excellent classification
- 0.80 - 0.90: Good classification
- 0.70 - 0.80: Fair classification
- 0.60 - 0.70: Poor classification
- 0.50 - 0.60: Failure

2.2 EXTREME GRADIENT BOOSTING AND LIGHT GRADIENT BOOSTING MACHINE

2.2.1 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is a machine learning method designed to address regression and classification

problems by building a Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT) model [4]. XGBoost improves upon the Gradient Boosting algorithm by employing ensemble learning to combine weak learners (e.g., decision trees) iteratively to form a strong learner. This process enhances the overall model performance by addressing errors from prior iterations [5].

The training of XGBoost involves minimizing an objective function defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\Phi) = \sum_{i=1}^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^T \Omega(f_k), \quad (23)$$

where $l(y_i, \hat{y}_i)$ represents the loss function measuring the error between actual (y_i) and predicted values (\hat{y}_i), and $\Omega(f_k)$ is the regularization term given by:

$$\Omega(f_k) = \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \|w\|^2, \quad (24)$$

with γ and λ being regularization hyperparameters, T the number of leaf nodes, and w the weights of the leaf nodes.

To optimize the tree structure, XGBoost calculates the gain (G), which evaluates the quality of a split:

$$G = \frac{(\sum_{i \in I_L} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I_L} h_i + \lambda} + \frac{(\sum_{i \in I_R} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I_R} h_i + \lambda} - \frac{(\sum_{i \in I} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I} h_i + \lambda}, \quad (25)$$

where I_L and I_R are indices of data points in the left and right child nodes, and g_i and h_i are the first and second derivatives of the loss function, respectively.

The predictive update in XGBoost is given by:

$$\hat{y}_i^{(t)} = \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)} + \eta f_t(x_i), \quad (26)$$

where η is the learning rate and $f_t(x_i)$ is the prediction of the tree at iteration t .

2.2.2 Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)

Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) is an efficient implementation of GBDT developed by Microsoft Research Asia. It is well-suited for handling large-scale datasets with high-dimensional features and offers faster training and lower memory usage compared to traditional GBDT implementations [13]. Key advantages of LightGBM include parallel learning capabilities, GPU support, and superior accuracy due to innovative algorithms.

LightGBM improves upon XGBoost through four major innovations:

1. Gradient-based One-Side Sampling (GOSS) balances sample selection and precision for tree splitting.
 2. Histogram-based splitting replaces the traditional pre-sorted approach, enabling faster computations at the cost of slight accuracy reduction.
 3. Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB) reduces feature dimensionality by combining mutually exclusive sparse features.
 4. Leaf-wise tree growth optimizes tree structure for maximum information gain but introduces potential overfitting.
- LightGBM employs leaf-wise tree growth, prioritizing splits with maximum gain to enhance accuracy. Predictions are updated iteratively:

$$\hat{y}_i^{(t)} = \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)} + \eta f_t(x_i), \quad (27)$$

where η is the learning rate and $f_t(x_i)$ represents the prediction at iteration t .

2.2.3 Algorithmic Steps

The steps for implementing XGBoost and LightGBM are as follows:

1. Initialize predictions \hat{y}_i with the average target value.
2. For each tree, compute gradients and Hessians:

$$g_i = \frac{\partial L(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i}, \quad h_i = \frac{\partial^2 L(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i^2}.$$

3. Construct the tree based on the chosen splitting strategy (gain for XGBoost or histogram-based for LightGBM).
4. Update predictions using the learning rate and the tree output.
5. Repeat until the number of estimators or convergence criteria are met.

The final model aggregates predictions from all trees:

$$F(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T \eta f_t(x). \quad (28)$$

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussions from the classification of stunting in Nusa Tenggara Timur using the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) methods. The discussion includes data description, preprocessing steps, model implementation, and evaluation.

3.1 Data Description

The dataset was sourced from the Nusa Tenggara Timur Provincial Health Office in 2024. It contains 349,528 samples of under-five children, represented by 7 features related to stunting status. The dataset used in this study was obtained from the Health Office of East Nusa

Tenggara Province under a confidentiality agreement. Due to privacy regulations and data sensitivity, the raw dataset cannot be shared publicly. However, summary statistics and preprocessing details are available upon request for academic purposes.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

The dataset underwent preprocessing, including *data cleaning*, *label encoding*, *handling class imbalance*, and *data splitting*.

3.2.1 Data Cleaning

The dataset was confirmed to be free of missing values, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Missing Values Across Variables

Variable	Missing Values
Gender	0
Birth Weight	0
Birth Height	0
Age at Measurement	0
Weight at Measurement	0
Height at Measurement	0
Stunting Status	0

3.2.2 Label Encoding

Categorical variables were converted into numerical values (Table 2).

Table 2 Label Encoding Transformation

Variable	Before	After
Gender	P, L	0, 1
Stunting Status	Yes, No	1, 0

3.2.3 Handling Class Imbalance

SMOTE was used to balance the dataset. Before SMOTE, 81.8% of samples were

non-stunted, and 18.2% were stunted. After SMOTE, both classes were balanced (Table 3).

Table 3 Class Distribution Before and After SMOTE

Class	Before	After
Non-stunted	285,788	285,788
Stunted	63,740	285,788

Fig. 6 Class Distribution Before SMOTE

Fig. 7 Class Distribution After SMOTE

3.2.4 Data Splitting

The dataset was split into training and testing sets using three ratios: 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40 (Table 4).

By employing balanced datasets and multiple splitting ratios, the machine learning models were trained and tested in a robust and reliable manner. This

Table 4 Data Splitting Ratios

Ratio	Training	Testing
80:20	432,599	108,149
70:30	378,524	162,224
60:40	324,449	216,299

ensured better generalization of the models and reduced biases in the classification results.

3.3 Implementation of *Extreme Gradient Boosting* (XGBoost)

After completing the data preprocessing steps, the classification task was carried out using the XGBoost model to classify stunting status into two categories: *Yes* (stunted) and *No* (not stunted). XGBoost operates by combining multiple decision trees to minimize residual errors iteratively, producing a robust and accurate predictive model.

3.3.1 Initialization

The initialization phase in XGBoost involves calculating the initial prediction probabilities, denoted as \hat{y}_i . This is computed as the mean of the target labels:

$$\hat{y}_i^{(0)} = \frac{\sum y_i}{N} \quad (29)$$

For the provided dataset, the calculation is as follows:

$$\hat{y}_i^{(0)} = \frac{1 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 1}{10} \quad (30)$$

This initial probability indicates a 50% likelihood of a child being stunted.

3.3.2 Gradient and Hessian Calculation

For each data point x_i , the gradient g_i and Hessian h_i are calculated as follows:

$$g_i = \hat{y}_i - y_i \quad (31)$$

$$h_i = \hat{y}_i(1 - \hat{y}_i) \quad (32)$$

Using the initialized prediction $\hat{y}_i^{(0)} = 0.5$ and the target values y_i from the dataset, the gradients and Hessians are calculated for each sample. An example calculation for a single data point $y_1 = 1$ is shown below:

$$g_1 = \hat{y}_1 - y_1 = 0.5 - 1 = -0.5 \quad (33)$$

$$h_1 = \hat{y}_1(1 - \hat{y}_1) = 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5) = 0.25 \quad (34)$$

Table 5 summarizes the computed gradients and Hessians for the dataset:

Table 5 Gradients and Hessians

Age	y_i	\hat{y}_i	g_i	h_i
27	1	0.5	-0.5	0.25
28	1	0.5	-0.5	0.25
31	0	0.5	0.5	0.25
32	0	0.5	0.5	0.25
40	0	0.5	0.5	0.25
42	0	0.5	0.5	0.25
51	1	0.5	-0.5	0.25
56	1	0.5	-0.5	0.25
60	0	0.5	0.5	0.25
65	1	0.5	-0.5	0.25

3.3.3 Gain Calculation and Tree Splitting

The next step involves calculating the gain G for potential splits in the decision tree. The gain is computed as:

$$G = \frac{(\sum_{i \in I_L} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I_L} h_i + \lambda} + \frac{(\sum_{i \in I_R} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I_R} h_i + \lambda} - \frac{(\sum_{i \in I} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in I} h_i + \lambda} \quad (35)$$

where I_L and I_R represent the left and right child nodes, respectively.

For a split threshold at Age < 53.5, the following calculations are performed:

$$S_L = \frac{(0.5 + 0.5 - 0.5 - 0.5 - 0.5)^2}{5 \cdot 0.25 + 0} = 0.143 \quad (36)$$

$$S_R = \frac{(0.5 - 0.5)^2}{2 \cdot 0.25 + 0} = 0.333 \quad (37)$$

$$S_{\text{root}} = \frac{(0)^2}{10 \cdot 0.25 + 0} = 0 \quad (38)$$

$$G = S_L + S_R - S_{\text{root}} = 0.476 \quad (39)$$

Based on the computed gain, a decision tree is constructed as illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8 Illustration of Decision Tree Split in XGBoost.

3.3.4 Output Value Calculation

The optimal output value w_j^* for each leaf node is calculated as:

$$w_j^* = \frac{\sum_{i \in I_j} g_i}{\sum_{i \in I_j} h_i + \lambda} \quad (40)$$

For a leaf node containing samples I_j :

$$w_1^* = \frac{-0.5 + -0.5 + 0.5}{3 \cdot 0.25 + 0} = -0.666 \quad (41)$$

This output value is used to update predictions iteratively until convergence is achieved.

3.3.5 Hyperparameter Tuning

Hyperparameter tuning was performed using grid search with 5-fold cross-validation. The tested parameter ranges are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6 Hyperparameter Ranges for XGBoost

Par	Range
<i>n_est</i>	{100, 200, 300}
<i>max_dep</i>	{8, 10, 12}
<i>lear_rate</i>	{0.01, 0.05, 0.1}
<i>gamma</i>	{0.0, 0.1, 0.2}

The optimal hyperparameters identified for a data split of 80:20 were:

- *n_estimators*: 100
- *max_depth*: 8
- *learning_rate*: 0.01
- *gamma*: 0.0

These values were used to train the final model, ensuring optimal performance.

3.4 Implementation of Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)

The LightGBM model was implemented for the binary classification of stunting status into stunted and non-stunted classes. LightGBM iteratively builds decision trees, starting with an initial prediction and updating predictions by calculating the gradient and hessian, which measure the difference and reliability of predictions. The model identifies the best split for features based on gain, updates the predictions using the leaf outputs,

and applies the sigmoid function to convert logits into probabilities. This iterative process continues until a stopping criterion is reached, forming a robust ensemble model for accurate classification.

Similar to the XGBoost implementation, the LightGBM model was evaluated using three train-test splits: 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40. Grid search was employed for hyperparameter tuning to optimize model performance.

The parameter ranges used during grid search are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Hyperparameter Ranges for LightGBM

Parameter	Values
<i>n_estimators</i>	{100, 200, 300}
<i>max_depth</i>	{3, 5, 10, 15}
<i>learning_rate</i>	{0.01, 0.05, 0.1}
<i>num_leaves</i>	{31, 50, 100}

The grid search process used 5-fold cross-validation, resulting in 540 iterations for each train-test split. The best parameters obtained from the grid search for each split are summarized in Tables 8

Table 8 Best Hyperparameters for LightGBM

Parameter	Best Value
<i>n_estimators</i>	100
<i>max_depth</i>	3
<i>learning_rate</i>	0.01
<i>num_leaves</i>	31

Using the optimized parameters, the final LightGBM model was trained on the full training dataset and evaluated on the test set. The evaluation focused on the model's ability to generalize and predict stunting status accurately. The results demonstrate that the LightGBM model,

with its hyperparameter tuning, achieved robust performance in classifying stunting status under different train-test splits.

3.5 XGBoost Model Performance

The classification was conducted with data splits of 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40 for training and testing sets. The corresponding confusion matrices for each split are shown in Figures 9, 10, and 11, respectively.

Fig. 9 Confusion Matrix for XGBoost (80:20 Split)

Fig. 10 Confusion Matrix for XGBoost (70:30 Split)

The evaluation metrics for each split were computed as follows:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{TN} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

Fig. 11 Confusion Matrix for XGBoost (60:40 Split)

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

The XGBoost model demonstrates stable and consistent performance across all data splits. The best performance is achieved with the 60:40 split, yielding an accuracy of 93.25%, precision of 91.91%, recall of 95.64%, and F1-Score of 93.74%. These results indicate that XGBoost is robust in classifying stunting data, even with varying training and testing distributions.

Additionally, the average training time for XGBoost across all splits is approximately 21.77 seconds, highlighting its computational efficiency. The hyperparameters used for each experiment were optimized using *grid search* and 5-fold *cross-validation*.

Overall, the XGBoost model demonstrates high predictive performance and computational efficiency, making it a reliable choice for stunting classification tasks.

3.6 LightGBM Model Performance

The classification of stunting and non-stunting classes was carried out using the

LightGBM model on datasets with splits of 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40 for training and testing. The confusion matrices for each split are shown in Figures 12, 13, and 14.

Fig. 12 Confusion Matrix for LightGBM (80:20 Split)

Fig. 13 Confusion Matrix for LightGBM (70:30 Split)

Fig. 14 Confusion Matrix for LightGBM (60:40 Split)

The LightGBM model demonstrates consistent performance across all data splits, with slight variations in evaluation metrics. The highest performance

was achieved with an 80:20 split, yielding an *accuracy* of 82.96%, *precision* of 83.09%, *recall* of 85.09%, and *F1-Score* of 84.08%.

Notably, LightGBM has a significantly faster training time compared to XGBoost, averaging approximately 2.32 seconds, which is almost ten times faster than XGBoost's 21.77 seconds. This makes LightGBM a suitable choice for applications where computational efficiency is critical. However, XGBoost outperformed LightGBM in all evaluation metrics, achieving its best *accuracy* of 93.25% and *F1-Score* of 93.74% with the 60:40 split.

While LightGBM excels in computational efficiency, XGBoost provides better classification accuracy and robustness. Depending on the application, a trade-off between performance and computational speed may guide model selection.

3.7 Comparison of XGBoost and LightGBM Model Performance

This section compares the performance of the XGBoost and LightGBM models in classifying stunting cases in Nusa Tenggara Timur. The comparison focuses on evaluation metrics, including *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall*, and *F1-Score*, as well as the training time required for each model.

For the 80:20 train-test split, the XGBoost model achieved an *accuracy* of 93.11%, indicating its ability to classify stunting cases correctly. It also obtained a *precision* of 91.70%, meaning it effectively identified stunting cases but still produced some false positives. The model had a *recall* of 95.61%, demonstrating its capability to identify most true stunting cases. The *F1-Score* was 93.62%, reflecting a strong balance between *precision* and *recall*. However, the training time

was 22.6 seconds, which is relatively long compared to LightGBM.

In contrast, the LightGBM model for the same 80:20 split showed an *accuracy* of 82.96%, which is significantly lower than XGBoost. Its *precision* was 83.09%, indicating a higher risk of false positives. The model achieved a *recall* of 85.09%, slightly lower than XGBoost, showing its limitations in capturing true stunting cases. The *F1-Score* was 84.08%, which is weaker than XGBoost’s performance. However, LightGBM excelled in training time, completing the process in just 2.07 seconds, making it nearly ten times faster than XGBoost.

For the 70:30 train-test split, XGBoost achieved an *accuracy* of 93.12%, a *precision* of 91.47%, a *recall* of 95.93%, and an *F1-Score* of 93.65%, with a training time of 21.26 seconds. These results confirm XGBoost’s consistent performance across different data splits. On the other hand, LightGBM had an *accuracy* of 83.03%, a *precision* of 83.42%, a *recall* of 84.75%, and an *F1-Score* of 84.07%, with a training time of 2.70 seconds. Although LightGBM’s performance was lower, it maintained its advantage in computational efficiency.

For the 60:40 train-test split, XGBoost achieved the highest performance, with an *accuracy* of 93.25%, a *precision* of 91.91%, a *recall* of 95.64%, and an *F1-Score* of 93.74%. The training time for this split was 21.45 seconds. Meanwhile, LightGBM had an *accuracy* of 82.56%, a *precision* of 83.19%, a *recall* of 83.95%, and an *F1-Score* of 83.57%, with a training time of 2.20 seconds.

In summary, XGBoost consistently outperformed LightGBM across all evaluation metrics, making it the superior model for accurate stunting classification. However, LightGBM demonstrated remarkable computational efficiency, requiring significantly less training time. For scenarios demanding high accuracy and recall, XGBoost is the recommended choice. On the other hand, for applications where computational resources or time are limited, LightGBM offers a viable alternative with reasonable performance.

3.8 ROC and AUC Analysis

This section presents the evaluation of the XGBoost and LightGBM models using ROC (*Receiver Operating Characteristic*) curves and AUC (*Area Under the Curve*) values for train-test splits of 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40. ROC curves illustrate the model’s ability to distinguish between stunting and non-stunting classes, while AUC values provide a quantitative measure of the overall classification performance.

3.8.1 XGBoost ROC and AUC Results

XGBoost consistently demonstrated high AUC values across all train-test splits, indicating excellent classification performance.

Fig. 15 ROC Curve for XGBoost (80:20 Split)

Fig. 16 ROC Curve for XGBoost (70:30 Split)

Fig. 19 ROC Curve for LightGBM (70:30 Split)

Fig. 17 ROC Curve for XGBoost (60:40 Split)

Fig. 20 ROC Curve for LightGBM (60:40 Split)

Table 9 AUC Results for XGBoost Model

TT	AUC	Accu (%)	Time
80:20	0.9848	93.11	22.6
70:30	0.9849	93.12	21.3
60:40	0.9849	93.25	21.5

Table 10 AUC Results for LightGBM Model

TT	AUC	Accu(%)	Time
80:20	0.9072	82.96	2.1
70:30	0.9079	83.03	2.7
60:40	0.9075	82.56	2.2

3.8.2 LightGBM ROC and AUC Results

LightGBM exhibited stable but slightly lower AUC values compared to XGBoost, indicating a reduced ability to distinguish between classes. However, it achieved much faster computational times.

Fig. 18 ROC Curve for LightGBM (80:20 Split)

From Tables 9 and 10, it is evident that XGBoost consistently outperformed LightGBM in terms of AUC values across all train-test splits. XGBoost achieved an AUC above 0.9848, while LightGBM's maximum AUC was 0.9079. Additionally, XGBoost had higher accuracy scores, reflecting its stronger classification capability.

However, LightGBM required significantly less training time—approximately 2 seconds compared to XGBoost's 22 seconds. This computational efficiency makes LightGBM suitable for time-sensitive applications, albeit with a slight trade-off in classification performance.

The ROC and AUC analysis underscores XGBoost's superior performance

in classification accuracy and AUC values. Conversely, LightGBM offers faster computational times, making it advantageous for scenarios where efficiency is paramount. Depending on the application’s requirements—whether prioritizing classification performance or computational speed—either model can be chosen to address the problem effectively.

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn from this study:

1. The *Extreme Gradient Boosting* (XGBoost) and *Light Gradient Boosting Machine* (LightGBM) methods were successfully applied to classify stunting data in East Nusa Tenggara. The preprocessing steps included data cleaning, label encoding, handling class imbalance using SMOTE, and data splitting. Both models classified the dataset into two classes: stunting and non-stunting.
2. XGBoost achieved superior performance with an accuracy of 93.11%, precision of 91.70%, recall of 95.61%, and F1-Score of 93.62%, with a training time of 22.6 seconds. LightGBM achieved an accuracy of 82.96%, precision of 83.09%, recall of 85.09%, and F1-Score of 84.08%, with a training time of 2.07 seconds. Thus, XGBoost outperformed LightGBM in classification performance, while LightGBM demonstrated faster training times.
3. Both XGBoost and LightGBM demonstrated reliable performance for stunting detection. However, XGBoost excelled in evaluation metrics, while

LightGBM was more computationally efficient. Model selection should depend on whether classification accuracy or computational efficiency is prioritized.

4. Based on the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) and Area Under Curve (AUC) analysis, XGBoost consistently achieved higher AUC values across all data splits (80:20, 70:30, and 60:40). For the 80:20 split, XGBoost recorded an AUC of 0.9848 compared to LightGBM’s 0.9072, further indicating XGBoost’s superior classification capability.

4.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed for future research:

1. Incorporate advanced feature engineering techniques to identify and utilize more informative features for improving model performance.
2. Explore additional hyperparameters such as *subsample*, *colsample_bytree*, and regularization parameters (*lambda* and *alpha*) for XGBoost. For LightGBM, parameters such as *min_child_samples*, *feature_fraction*, and *bagging_fraction* should also be considered.
3. Evaluate the models on datasets with different characteristics to assess the generalization capabilities of XGBoost and LightGBM.

5 Acknowledgments

The authors express their gratitude to Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia, for providing support and facilities throughout the research. We also extend our appreciation to the Health Office of East

Nusa Tenggara Province for their cooperation and data provision, as well as to the Indonesia Endowment Funds for Education (LPDP) for funding this research. Special thanks go to our academic advisor, for his invaluable guidance, insights, and encouragement, which greatly contributed to the completion of this study.

References

- [1] Beal, T., Tumilowicz, A., Sutrisna, A., Izwardy, D., & Neufeld, L. M. (2018). A review of child stunting determinants in Indonesia. *Maternal & Child Nutrition*, 14(4), e12617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mcn.12617>
- [2] Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS). (2021). Prevalensi Stunting di Indonesia Tahun 2021. Jakarta: BPS Indonesia.
- [3] Cady, F. (2017). *The Data Science Handbook*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [4] Cherif, I. L., & Kortebi, A. (2019). On using extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) machine learning algorithm for home network traffic classification. In *2019 Wireless Days (WD)* (pp. 1–6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WD.2019.8734232>
- [5] Chen, T., & Guestrin, C. (2016). XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (pp. 785–794). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939785>
- [6] Claesen, M., & De Moor, B. (2015). Hyperparameter search in machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1502.02127*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1502.02127>
- [7] Dangeti, P. (2017). *Statistics for Machine Learning: Techniques for exploring supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning models with Python and R*. Packt Publishing.
- [8] Gorunescu, F. (2011). *Data Mining: Concepts, Models, and Techniques*. Springer.
- [9] Han, J., Kamber, M., & Pei, J. (2012). *Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques* (3rd ed.). Elsevier.
- [10] Jange, B. (2022). Prediksi harga saham Bank BCA menggunakan XGBoost. *ARBITRASE: Journal of Economics and Accounting*, 3(2), 495–503.
- [11] James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2013). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R*. Springer.
- [12] Kasanah, A. N., Muladi, & Pujiyanto, U. (2019). Penerapan teknik SMOTE untuk mengatasi imbalance class dalam klasifikasi objektivitas berita online menggunakan algoritma KNN. *Jurnal RESTI (Rekayasa Sistem dan Teknologi Informasi)*, 3(2), 196–201.
- [13] Ke, G., Meng, Q., Finley, T., Wang, T., Chen, W., Ma, W., Ye, Q., & Liu, T. Y. (2017). LightGBM: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 30, 3146–3154.
- [14] Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. (2020). Peraturan

- Menteri Kesehatan Nomor 2 Tahun 2020 tentang Standar Antropometri Anak. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia.
- [15] Kusuma, S. T., & Sasongko, T. B. (2023). Optimasi K-Nearest Neighbor dengan Grid Search CV pada prediksi kanker paru-paru. *Indonesian Journal of Computer Science*, 12(4), 2162.
- [16] Lopez, V., et al. (2013). An insight into classification with imbalanced data: Empirical results and current trends on using data intrinsic characteristics. *Elsevier Ltd.*, Spain.
- [17] Ooba, H., Maki, J., Tabuchi, T., & Masuyama, H. (2023). Partner relationships, hopelessness, and health status strongly predict maternal well-being: An approach using light gradient boosting machine. *Scientific Reports*, 13(17032), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-44410-1>
- [18] Rahman, M. S., Howlader, T., Masud, M. S., & Rahman, M. L. (2021). Association of low birth weight with malnutrition in children under five years in Bangladesh: Do mother's education, socio-economic status, and birth interval matter? *PLOS ONE*, 16(6), e0253172. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253172>
- [19] Ramalingam, K., Yadalam, P. K., Ramani, P., Krishna, M., Hafedh, S., Badnjević, A., Cervino, G., & Minervini, G. (2024). Light gradient boosting-based prediction of quality of life among oral cancer-treated patients. *BMC Oral Health*, 24(349), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-024-04050-x>
- [20] Rizky, P. S., Hirzi, R. H., & Hidayaturrohman, U. (2022). Perbandingan metode LightGBM dan XGBoost dalam menangani data dengan kelas tidak seimbang. *J Statistika*, 5(2), 228–236.
- [21] Rufo, D. D., Debelee, T. G., Iben-thal, A., & Negera, W. G. (2021). Diagnosis of diabetes mellitus using gradient boosting machine (Light-GBM). *Diagnostics*, 11(9), 1714. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11091714>
- [22] Saputra, G. H., Wigena, A. H., & Sartono, B. (2019). Penggunaan support vector regression dalam pemodelan indeks saham syariah Indonesia dengan algoritme grid search. *Indonesian Journal of Statistics and Its Applications*, 3(2), 148–160.
- [23] Shen, L., Huang, Z., Wang, W., & Liu, H. (2023). Predicting stunting in children under five years old using machine learning: A case study in Papua New Guinea. *Children*, 10, e0342. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10030342>
- [24] Ozdemir, S. (2017). *Principles of Data Science: Learn the techniques, tools, and programming languages you need to analyze and visualize data*. Birmingham, UK: Packt Publishing.
- [25] Ramadanti, E., Dinathi, D. A., Aditya, C. S. K., & Chandranegara, D. R. (2024). Diabetes disease detection classification using

- Light Gradient Boosting (LightGBM) with hyperparameter tuning. *Sinkron: Jurnal dan Penelitian Teknik Informatika*, 8(2).
- [26] Sinha, B. B., Ahsan, M., & Danalakshmi, R. (2023). LightGBM empowered by whale optimization for thyroid disease detection. *Bharati Vidyapeeth's Institute of Computer Applications and Management*, 15(4), 2053–2062.
- [27] Sullivan, W. (2017). *Machine Learning for Absolute Beginners: A Step-by-Step Guide to Algorithms for Supervised and Unsupervised Learning with Real-World Applications*. Raymond Kazuya.
- [28] Suyanto. (2019). *Data Mining untuk Klasifikasi dan Klasterisasi Data*. Penerbit Informatika, Bandung.
- [29] Thabtah, F., et al. (2019). Data imbalance in classification: Experimental evaluation. *Elsevier Ltd.*, New Zealand.
- [30] UNICEF. (2020). *Improving child nutrition: The achievable imperative for global progress*. UNICEF.
- [31] Wamani, H., Åström, A. N., Peterson, S., Tumwine, J. K., & Tylleskär, T. (2007). Boys are more stunted than girls in Sub-Saharan Africa: A meta-analysis of 16 demographic and health surveys. *BMC Pediatrics*, 7, Article number: 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2431-7-17>
- [32] Wang, M., Li, X., Zhang, C., & Zhao, Z. (2022). Human health risk identification of petrochemical sites based on extreme gradient boosting. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 233, 113332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.113332>
- [33] Wei, C., Zhang, L., Feng, Y., Ma, A., & Kang, Y. (2022). Machine learning model for predicting acute kidney injury progression in critically ill patients. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 22(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-021-01740-2>
- [34] World Health Organization (WHO). (2022). *WHO child growth standards: Length/height-for-age, weight-for-age, weight-for-length, weight-for-height and body mass index-for-age: Methods and development*. Geneva: World Health Organization.
- [35] Yang, H., Chen, Z., Li, Y., & Zhou, L. (2023). Predicting coronary heart disease using an improved LightGBM model: Performance analysis and comparison. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2023, Article ID 23366, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/23366>